

Student-Teacher Ratio, Parental Education and Academic Outcomes in Basic Science in Selected Local Government Area of Oyo State

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Abstract

The study analyzed the student-teacher ratio, parental education and academic outcomes in basic science in selected Local Government Area of Oyo State. An ex post facto research design was employed using 258 students selected from three Local Governments Area of Oyo State through a purposive sampling technique across nine schools, three schools each in each Local Government Area of Oyo State. In each school, 43 male and female students were involved in the study making a total of 86 Basic Science Students in each school. Basic Science Performance Test (BSPT) was used to obtain data which was scored in percentage with the difference in student-teacher ratio per school. Multiple regression statistical tools were used for data to test the hypotheses at $P 0.05$ level of significance. The results revealed that there were significant relationship between the student's academic outcome in Basic Science and the student-teacher ratio and parents' year of schooling ($t=0.001$, $p<0.05$), that is both independent variables can jointly predict the academic outcomes of learners with parents' years of schooling showing more significant effect than student-teacher ratio. The findings established the immense value of the student-teacher ratio and parents' years of schooling to the schools, stakeholders, and government. It was recommended that educational planners and policy makers pay prompt attention to this student-teacher ratio issue, sticking to the proper implementation of UNESCO of 25-26:1 and National Policy on Education recommendations which suggested 30 students per teacher in all schools among others.

Keywords: Students-Teacher Ratio, Parent Years of Schooling, Academic Outcomes, Basic Science

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Introduction

Education is a foundation for development and progress of any society. It is a base upon which the whole building of human development stands. Getting proper education is necessary for success in life just like the food is necessary for the healthy body. Education leaves long-lasting impact on global development therefore, higher education plays a transformative role in shaping individuals, societies, and economics (Gupta, 2023). Science is a systematic study of the natural world through observation, experimentation, and analysis. Science is based on fact, not opinion or preferences. It involves the use of evidence logic, and the scientific method to understand and explain the various phenomena and laws that govern our universe. Science education refers to the teaching and learning of scientific concepts, principles, and processes. This is done through Basic Science a subject taught in Basic classes (Basic 1-9). It aims to develop scientific literacy and critical thinking skills among students. Science education is important as it helps individuals understand and appreciate the natural worlds, fosters scientific inquiry and problem-solving skills, and promotes scientific literacy in the society. It equips students with the knowledge, empowering their minds with skills necessary to transform their community. Basic Science and Technology then Integrated Science was introduced by the Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) in 1972 (Iwuyi, 2012 in Amuda, 2021). The program has been in existence for over 50 years with reforms and innovation from Nature study to Integrated Science to Basic Science and to Basic Science and Technology in Junior Secondary Schools, while Integrated Science remain a course in higher institutions and Basic Science and Basic Science and Technology are being taught separately in Junior Secondary Schools.

Science Education is defined as the study of the connection between science as a discipline and the application of educational principles to comprehend science teaching and learning in the classroom (Dabah, 2016). Therefore, science education acquaints students with certain basic knowledge, skills and attitudes needed for future work in science and science related fields. The impact of science education on national development could be felt in several ways: as it provides humanity with knowledge about the environment, attitudes and values for social living, knowledge and skills to explore and transform resources, effect change in quality of life and improve the economy (Udofia, 2010). However, most governments throughout the globe spend a large portion of their bud get on educational resources. They make judgments on how to provide resources and inputs to help students attain higher levels of success and performance. Education quality is critical for strategic planning of academic goals and keeping up with the developed world's pace. Similarly, the academic performance of students is the yardstick for testing the educational quality of a nation as declared by Nwokocha and Amadike, (2005). Also, Oni (2014), remarked that acquisition of knowledge in the subjects is one of the means by which the nation hopes to attain the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) in 2015 and the important targets of the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategies (NERDC 2014). In one word Basic Science and Technology is supported to contribute to the achievement of the national education goals by providing the required technical knowledge and vocational skills. Hence, Ajisegiri (2010) observes that:-

“If the quality of educational at the primary level is poor it will be foolish to expect that the standard at the secondary level will be high because it is the primary school that feeds the secondary. In the same vein, if the standard of the secondary level is poor, we should also expect that the quality at tertiary level will be poor, so, in ensuring that we have a high quality of education in the country, it is incumbent on government to see that the standard in high is all levels”

Also, Adegoke, (2015) stressed that the importance of Basic Science in Schools is not only for obtaining certificate but also for producing future scientists in all spheres of life that will bring about national developments in all her ramifications. The future scientists begin their scientific experience from the study of Basic Science in Junior Secondary Schools (JSS) which should be activities based, and they continue with this experience at the higher education levels including Senior Secondary Schools (SSS). Basic Science enables students to develop knowledge and understanding of the application of scientific knowledge to everyday life activities. It also helps in the acquisition of life-long learning skills for solving everyday problems. Students develop positive attitude towards science and places high values on scientific activities. It further helps students to develop and appreciate the role of science in fostering a safe and healthy lifestyle. Also, enable individuals to function effectively within increasingly technological and scientific global environment as well as the appreciation of the contribute to sustainable development.

Therefore, in order for science and technology to take its firm shape in our society, the poor state of Basic Science education must be addressed. One of the many ways for achieving this noble goal is through effective instructional strategies. The Pride of Educational Institutions is based not only in the number but also on the quality of the output at all levels. However, most governments throughout the globe spend a large portion of their budget on educational resources. They make judgments on how to provide resource inputs to help students attain higher levels of success and performance. Education quality in crucial for strategic planning of academic goals and keeping up with the developed world’s pace. Similarly, the academic performance of students is the yardstick for testing the educational quality of nation, declared Nwokocha and Amadike (2005)

As number of students in a classroom grows, so does the size of the class and the student-to-teacher ratio become a concern. The number of students per instructor, (teacher) or average number of students a teacher educates in a school, is referred to as the student-teacher ratio. According to Kezar, Grave and Rasusher, (2006), the quality of education is influenced by a variety of factors. Teacher educational quality, student’s intellectual quotient, students’ health, quality teaching in the school, school location, social environmental factors, curriculum, the types of instruction i.e., teacher-centered (e.g. pupils listen, answer questions, practice, etc.) or students centered (e.g. problem-solving, creative projects, etc) as well as student-teacher ratio are just among factors to be consider.

Teacher at schools with a lower student-to-teacher ratio have more time to spend with each student and check on the development of each student for whom they are responsible, allowing them to give more personalized instruction that is more appropriate for each student. The National

Policy on Education (NPC 2014) stipulates that a class size of not more than 30 students be maintained, the average class size in most institutions in the country surpasses 50, most especially in public primary and secondary schools. The scenario hurts the average amount of classroom space available per student. Those students on the other hand required a comfortable environment to learn. The classroom utilization rate in most public secondary schools in the country is always high; this is because most schools have more pupils than they can accommodate or have less required number of teachers resulting in an uncondusive environment for academic activities (Dave, 2008).

Parents who have undergone learning will strive to support their children to better academic achievement, because, there is direct relationship between parents' educational attainment and student academic success at school. What the child learns at home and how his/her parents motivate him towards learning will contribute to the child's success or failure in the school. (Adegoke and Adeyi, 2015). In most cases, science or non-science-oriented and the level of parents' education achievement, do depend on how parents inculcate learning into their children for a better future, while Akinsanya, Ajayi and Salomi, (2014) suggested that a wider range of parental involvement I n students' motivation even if parents are unable to assist their children with a specific subject area or skill, they can still play a vital role by encouraging and motivating students. The study emphasizes teacher students and parent relationship as tools that can bring innovation and enhanced children learning outcomes in various subject, especially science subject and such relationship can result into: -

- i. Removing the fear and stress from student's mind
- ii. Developing a common language and mutual understanding
- iii. Reducing the communication gap.
- iv. Providing a perfect environment for learning (Abudu & Gbadamosi, 2014.).

There are many types of parents in the society. Some parents are educated while some are illiterate. Parents' average year of schooling will motivate the interest of a child. Parents' achievement directs learners to achieve their goals and objectives towards education and determines that level at which a student or learner can go in education activities Adegoke and Adeyi, (2015) Science-oriented parents with a good number of years of schooling provide information and ideas to gear up educational attitudes about how to help their children at home with homework and other curriculum related activities decisions. They provide information and skills required by their children to have a better academic outcome in Basic Science.

However, education focuses on the influence and progress of the students at school as well as his academic performance. Therefore, a student-teacher ratio and parents' years of schooling provide leverage for learners' basic training and discipline. Parents have been a major source from which students copy ways of behavior, the students educational level condition will determine parental responsibility as far as education is concerned as the level of education will motivate their involvement in the student's education which in turn has effects on the academic outcome in Basic Science (Taft, Perkowski & Martin 2011). Moreso, Behaviorist theory asserts that knowledge is

finite. Learning is said to be over, observable and measurable using empirical methods. Learning is influenced by external factors, as opposed to internal though processes of intrinsic motivation. Learning is rewarded to encourage desirable results. Extrinsic motivation derives students to do things for tangible rewards or pressures.

Effects of Students-Teacher Ratio on Learner Academic Outcomes in Basic Science

The pupil-teacher ratio, which refers to the number of students per teacher in a classroom, has a significant impact on academic performance in basic science and other subjects. Taft, Perkowski & Martin (2011) outlines the following ways in which student-teacher ratio can affect academic performance in basic science:

- i. **Provision of Individualized Attention:** Student-teacher-ratio typically allows teachers to provide more individualized attention to each student. In basic science classes, this can mean more opportunities for students to ask questions, receive personalized explanations, and engage in hands-on activities or experiments. This individualized attention can enhance understanding and retention of basic scientific concepts.
- ii. **Good Classroom Management:** Smaller class sizes generally result in better classroom management and discipline. With fewer students to manage, teachers can spend more time-teaching and less time dealing with behavioural issues. This conducive leaning environment can foster greater focus and participation in basic science lessons.
- iii. **Fostering Interactive Learning:** In classrooms with lower student-teacher ratios, there may be more opportunities for interactive learning experiences such as group discussions, collaborative projects, and demonstrations. These activities can facilitate a deeper understanding of basic science concepts by encouraging active participation and peer-to-peer learning.
- iv. **Ensuring Feedback and Assessment:** With fewer students to assess, teachers can provide more timely and detailed feedback on assignments, quizzes, and tests. This feedback loop is essential for student learning and improvement in basic science subjects, as it helps students identify areas of strength and weakness and adjust their studying accordingly.
- v. **Improving Teacher Professional Development:** Schools with lower student-teacher ratios may have more resources available for teacher's professional development. This can lead to more effective teaching strategies, better utilization of educational technology, and enhanced content knowledge in basic science among educators, ultimately benefiting student learning outcomes.

Parental Level of Schooling and Effects on Learner Academic Outcomes in Basic Science

According to some studies, a child's academic success is influenced by the extent of parental participation (Oyedare, Ogunjimi and Durojaiye, 2016). Parents with a good number of years of schooling influence the academic outcome of their children in basic science in the following ways among others;

- i. The parents as a Role Model: Parents with higher levels of education often value leaning and education more, which can serve as a positive influence on their children. Children may be more likely to emulate their parents' attitudes towards education and academic success.
- ii. Provision of Sound Educational Support: Parents with higher levels of education are generally better equipped to provide academic support to their children. They provide financial resources, educational materials, such as books, educational toys, and supplementary learning programs. They may have a deeper understanding of the subject matter and be able to assist with homework and provide additional resources such as opportunities like museum visits, field trips, excursions, or science camps, which can enhance their children's understanding of basic science concepts. (Olajide, 2019)
- iii. Expectations and Aspirations: Parents with higher levels of education often have higher expectations for their children's academic achievement. This can create a supportive environment where children are encouraged to excel in their studies and pursue higher education, including in STEM fields like Basic Science.(Enyinna and Jessica, 2021).
- iv. Good Language and Communication Skills: Parents with higher levels of education may have better communication skills, which can facilitate more effective communication with teachers and support their children's language development, Strong language skills are essential for understanding complex scientific concepts and communicating ideas effectively.

Significance of the Study

The findings from this study will provide knowledge and information and also educate parents on the needs and importance of getting involved in the education of their children making, their years of schooling counts on the academic outcome of the children. The findings of the study will inform policy decisions on the optimal student-teacher ratio and the importance of parental education, thus, reducing the academic outcome gap created by these factors. More so, the findings of the study will provide a base for future research

Research Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between the student-teacher ratio and learner's academic outcomes.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between parents' years of schooling and learner's academic outcome

Methodology

This study examined the effect of student-teacher ratio and Parents' Year of Schooling on the academic outcome of learners in Basic Science in Oyo State. Multistage sampling procedure was adopted for the study. Three Local Government were randomly selected from Oyo Metropolis. Three schools were randomly selected from each of the local government areas selected namely, Afijio, Oyo West and Oyo East Local Government Areas of Oyo State. All the Junior Secondary School II Students were adopted for the study with each of the sampled schools. An intact class

was used to select 43 male and 43 females, making 86 students from each school and the nine schools make total of 258 subjects selected. Simple random sampling and purposive sampling technique for the 9 schools sampled for the study. Basic Science Performance Test (BSPT) was used to obtain data, and this was scored in percentage with differences in student-teacher ratio preschool. The survey on the bio-data of the students and that of their parent’s average year of schooling were obtained through questionnaire and it was analyzed using descriptive analysis, while multiple regression statistical tools for data analysis were used to answer the research questions and also to test the formulated hypotheses at α 0.05; level of significance.

Results and Interpretation

Research Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between the student-teacher ratio and learners academic outcomes.

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Regression	1656.305	2	828.153	22.707	.001 ^b
	Residual	255.295	7	36.471		
	Total	1911.600	-8			

a. Dependent Variable: Scores

b. Predictors: (Constant) average parents’ years of schooling student teacher ratio

The ANOVA table above shows a Significant Value of 0.01 which is less than the significant level of 0.05, therefore, the independent variable of the students-teacher ratio, and Parents’ years of schooling can jointly predict Children’s performance.

Research Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between parents’ years of schooling and learner’s academic outcome.

Model Summary

Change Statistics

Model	R	R. Square	Adjusted Square	R. Std. Error of the Estimate	Square Change	F change	Df1	Df2	Sig. Change	F
1.	.931	.866	.828	6.03010	.866	22.707	2	7	.011	

A predictors: (Constant), average parents years of schooling, student teacher ratio

The results from the table above shows the R Square value to be 0.866 and taken it to percentage by multiplying by 100. We have 86.6% of the joint independent variables predicts learners’ academic outcome. Therefore, the proportion of variance is equal to 86.6%.

Testing the formulated hypotheses H₀₁& H₀₂: That there is no significant relationship between the student-teacher ratio and learners’ academic outcome and also that there is no significant relationship between parents’ average years of schooling and learners’ academic outcome respectively. The results from Table 2 show the proportion of variance of the learner’s academic outcomes with the linear combination of students-teacher ratio and parents’ year of schooling. A significant value of 0.01 which is less than the significant level of 0.05 the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is hereby accepted, since, the students-teacher ratio and parents’ years of schooling can jointly predict learners’ performance. Also, the student-teacher ratio and parents’ years of schooling both account for 86.66% of effects on learners’ academic outcomes in Basic Science.

a. Dependent Variable: scores

The result reveals that the relative contribution of each of the independent variables of the students-teacher ratio, and parents' years of schooling as it predicts the Children's performance, going by the Beta values, students- (792) better predicts learners' academic outcome than students-teacher ratio (247). The teacher ratio is 247 and Parents' years of school are 729.

Discussion of the findings

The results of the study have established that the student-teacher ratio and average parents' years of schooling have positive influences on the academic outcomes of students in Basic Science which were also statistically significant according to the result of the findings, this is in line with the submission of Oyedare, Ogunjinmi, and Durojaiye, (2016). Bello, Aderanti, Adewole, Adeoye, and Bankole (2019) also, Parents with a good number of years of schooling influence the academic outcome of their children in basic science in the following ways among others.

Coefficients

	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients			95.0% Interval Lower	Confidential for B Upper
Model	B	St. Error	Beta	T	Sig.	Bound	Bound
1. (Constant)	12.117	20.428		.593	.572	-36.188	60.422
Student teacher ratio	-.640	.401	-.247	-1.596	.155	-1.589	.308
Average_parents_years_of_schooling	4.797	.939	-.792	5.108	.001	2.577	7.018

Conclusion

The Research established that the student-teacher ratio and parents' average years of schooling and their involvement in their children's education positively correlate with the learner's academic outcome. Parents with more years of schooling have higher levels of education and may be more likely to be involved in their children's schooling, attending parent-teacher conferences,

and advocating for their children's educational needs. Learners from families with low average years of schooling and those with a high ratio of students-teacher per class can still excel academically with the right support systems in place, such as dedicated teachers, access to quality education, and community resources. Additionally, individual differences, socioeconomic factors, and other external influences can also play significant roles in shaping learners' academic outcome in Basic Science. These submissions are in line with Adegoke and Adeyi (2015), which corroborated that achievement does depend on how parents inculcate learning into their children for better learning outcome.

Recommendation

- i. Government should ensure that policies and recommendations are implemented most especially, UNESCO recommendation on an average of 26 students per teacher.
- ii. Parents should be more involved in the education of the children most importantly those in sciences to improve their academic performance.
- iii. Parents should be informed about benefits of furthering their education through Part-time, Sandwich, Distance Learning or through Adult Education class in order to increase their average years of schooling, and be orientated about their involvement to improve the academic performance of their children

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